

Democratizing AI, making geotechnology accessible to all

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Abstract

Geospatial analysis, essential for identifying patterns and spatial relationships, faces considerable challenges due to the technical complexity associated with handling tools like Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and specialized query languages. This technical barrier limits access to a broader audience, preventing geospatial data from being fully exploited for strategic decision-making. In this context, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) emerges as a promising approach to democratize the use of these resources, expanding their social and economic impact. This study proposes an innovative solution combining AI and NLP, utilizing the Gemini model to convert natural language questions into high-performance SQL queries, eliminating the need for advanced GIS knowledge. The developed modular architecture, composed of a User Interface, AI API, and Geographic Database, promotes intuitive data access, facilitating digital inclusion. Preliminary results indicate an 87% success rate in query conversion, demonstrating the viability of the approach. It concludes that the synergy between AI and GIS not only simplifies geospatial data analysis but also broadens access to information for diverse audiences, enhancing its application in areas such as urban planning, environmental management, and disaster response. This study thus lays a solid foundation for future improvements aimed at refining model accuracy and expanding the available database, contributing to more robust and inclusive geospatial data analysis solutions.

1. Introduction

Geospatial analysis is a method that employs maps and visual representations to identify and display geographic patterns, trends, and relationships. It is an approach that reveals strategic insights, facilitating the establishment of actions with greater speed, simplicity, and precision.

According to Alshaer et al. (2024), spatial evaluation enhances the possibilities of traditional investigation by providing a deeper understanding of the complexity of the locations where activities are occurring, should occur, or could occur. When enhanced, it significantly improves planning and operational efficiency in organizations, offering new knowledge and essential values for the optimization of strategic procedures.

About 80% of the data generated and used in various fields of life and science is geospatial in nature (Dasgupta, 2017). However, this content is not fully explored, as processing and interpretation often require advanced technical knowledge in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Ramezan et al., 2024; Rosa, 2013) and proficiency in specialized query languages such as SQL. For example, according to Sousa et al. (2024), access to the various reference databases from multiple public repositories is only possible with specific knowledge of the SQL language.

The requirement for specialized qualifications presents a significant barrier for users lacking technical skills, limiting access to and utilization of geospatial inputs to a restricted audience. This difficulty results in the underutilization of data for communicating informed decisions, as many professionals and organizations struggle to translate it into practical insights.

In other words, the lack of familiarity with tools such as GIS and specialized query languages like SQL can lead to excessive reliance on technical specialists, resulting in slower and more expensive processes. Furthermore, this technological barrier prevents the democratization of knowledge, restricting the ability of various sectors—from urban planning to environmental management—to make judgments based on geographic evidence in a timely and autonomous manner.

Given this scenario, and considering the technological advances and digital transformation that have significantly increased the availability of sensors for collecting spatial variables, the need for sophisticated interpretation methods becomes evident, highlighting the demand for integrating artificial intelligence (AI) tools.

The AI has the potential to transform data analysis and interpretation, offering agile and efficient solutions to overcome existing technological barriers and democratize access to information (Ivić, 2019). By enabling machines and devices to perform functions akin to human reasoning (Melit & Kalogirou, 2007), AI simplifies understanding, facilitates diagnoses, and expands accessibility and applicability to a wider and more diverse audience (Ivić, 2019).

The democratization of geospatial technologies is notably important in several aspects of contemporary society. Socially and economically, these technologies empower individuals, especially marginalized groups, by allowing them to access and interpret information, facilitating their active participation in decision-making. In the environmental field, democratizing these technologies enables the development of more effective planning, the implementation of policies aimed at minimizing environmental impact, and the promotion of conservation.

Moreover, it contributes to preparation for extreme events, the creation of evacuation routes, and the implementation of risk mitigation strategies, resulting in more efficient crisis management.

In today's technological era, access to information is recognized as a fundamental right, as stated in Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), which asserts: "Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive, and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers." Digital inclusion is achieved when individuals are integrated into the technological context and fully exercise their citizenship (Bonilla & Pretto, 2011).

As technology advances and becomes increasingly integrated into our daily lives, the ability to access and comprehend digital information becomes essential for active citizenship and the full exercise of rights and responsibilities. The democratization of technology, as emphasized by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, allows individuals from diverse backgrounds and abilities to benefit from opportunities for learning, decision-making, and civic engagement. Therefore, ensuring access and digital inclusion not only reinforces fundamental human rights but also drives social and economic progress, creating a more just and informed society for all.

In addition, democratizing geospatial information catalyzes innovation by expanding access to advanced AI tools and sophisticated algorithms. This advancement enables the development of disruptive solutions, improves operational efficiency, and promotes continuous growth in various sectors.

In this context, the present study aims to develop and evaluate an innovative technological solution designed to simplify geospatial analysis by integrating advanced techniques in natural language processing (NLP) and artificial intelligence (AI). The central proposal is to create a tool that allows ordinary users, without specialized technical training, to efficiently access and intuitively understand geospatial data and information. This objective is achieved by eliminating the need for advanced knowledge in GIS tools or complex SQL queries.

The proposed innovation lies in the combination of NLP with geospatial analysis, providing a new approach to exploring and visualizing complex data. As users interact with the database through a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface, the solution significantly reduces the learning curve associated with traditional GIS tools and facilitates access to detailed insights without requiring advanced technical skills.

2. Development

The system was developed using a modular architecture, structured into four main components, interconnected to ensure efficient and precise interaction with geospatial data: User Interface (Frontend), API (Backend), Integration with Artificial Intelligence (Gemini), and Geographic Database. Each of these modules plays a crucial role in the system's functioning, ranging from the graphical interface that facilitates user interaction to the artificial intelligence that converts questions into optimized SQL queries.

2.1. User Interface (Frontend)

The graphical user interface (GUI) is a key component in the effectiveness and usability of web maps, as it plays an essential

role in the user's interaction with the map (Cybulski and Horbiński, 2020). In this work, the interface was implemented using advanced technologies like React, enabling users to interact with the application through a chat interface, allowing them to pose questions and visualize geospatial data dynamically, intuitively, and interactively. Elements such as interactivity, efficiency, consistency, familiarity, and accessibility were considered fundamental principles guiding the design of the graphical interface (Cybulski and Horbiński, 2020). In line with these principles, the following attributes were rigorously incorporated: (a) an interactive chat that allows the user to interact with the artificial intelligence by asking questions and receiving textual responses; (b) a dynamic map for viewing geospatial data; (c) a dynamic table for non-geometric data visualization; and (d) advanced controls for map visualization adjustments and management of loaded layers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Composition of the user interface.
Source: The authors.

2.2. API (Backend)

The API Backend was implemented using the Flask framework, which is widely recognized for its simplicity and flexibility, making it one of the most used frameworks for Python development (Copperwaite & Leifer, 2015). This application forms the system's core, mediating the interaction between the user interface, the AI model, and the geographic database by processing queries and returning results efficiently. Its functions include: (a) receiving and preprocessing user queries; (b) interacting with the AI model to obtain SQL queries; (c) validating and executing SQL queries in the geographic database; (d) processing and formatting query results; (e) implementing security measures and performance optimizations; and (f) managing user sessions and authentication.

2.3. Integration with Artificial Intelligence (Gemini)

Artificial intelligence was integrated using Google's Gemini model, one of the most advanced AI tools of its generation, known for its comprehensive capabilities and superior performance across various domains (Team et al., 2023). This module is responsible for converting natural language questions into high-performance SQL queries. Its primary functions include: (a) configuring and maintaining the prompt for interaction with the Gemini API; and (b) defining the formatting and structure of the responses generated by Gemini.

2.4. Geographic Database

The Geographic Database was implemented in PostgreSQL/PostGIS to store and manage geospatial and tabular data used in queries and interactive visualization. Among spatial databases, PostgreSQL stands out for incorporating advanced spatial functionalities. PostGIS, one of the first and most robust

implementations of these capabilities, offers a high level of optimization for spatial queries and a wide range of functions. It is also open-source software, allowing modifications and optimizations, making it especially relevant for this study (Agarwal & Rajan, 2016).

3. System Workflow

The operational workflow follows these steps: (1) The user accesses the graphical interface and enters their question; (2) The question is transmitted to the API, where it undergoes verification; (3) The API forwards the query to the Gemini model; (4) Gemini processes the input and generates a response in a predefined format; (5) The API processes the received response. If the response contains a query, the API executes the query on the geographic database; (6) The API processes the result obtained. If the result includes geometric data, a GeoJSON file is generated; (7) The API returns the response to the system; (8) The frontend displays the requested information on the screen. If the response contains geometry, the frontend renders it (Figure 2).

Figure 2. System workflow detail.
Source: The authors.

It is important to highlight that the interaction between these modules is essential to ensure the system operates efficiently. The User Interface provides an intuitive and accessible user experience; the API manages the data and business logic; and the Artificial Intelligence Integration intelligently converts questions into geographic SQL queries. This modular architecture simplifies system development and maintenance, facilitating future expansion by allowing the addition of new features to the interface, continuous API improvement, and integration with more advanced AI models.

3.1. AI Consumption API: Initial Setup

To enable the central functionality of the software, which consists of converting natural language into SQL queries for geospatial data, it was imperative to implement a robust API dedicated to Artificial Intelligence consumption. For this purpose, Google's Gemini, a sophisticated language model, was chosen. The initial setup of the API involved the following steps:

- **Environment Configuration:** A secure environment was established to ensure communication with the Gemini API and to configure the necessary credentials for authentication and authorization with Google tools. The development using Flask technology required the configuration of a Python 3.9 environment, complemented by the following libraries: (a) Flask (version 3.0.3) – essential for the development of APIs and web applications; (b) Flask-Cors (version 4.0.1) – a Flask extension that simplifies Cross-Origin Resource Sharing

(CORS) configuration for the application; (c) google-generativeai (version 0.7.2) – enabling integration with Google's generative artificial intelligence services for tasks such as natural language processing and text generation; (d) psycopg2 (version 2.9.9) – performs SQL queries, manages transactions, handles binary data, and performs database-related operations for PostgreSQL; (e) geojson (version 3.1.0) – facilitates the creation, manipulation, and analysis of geospatial data in GeoJSON format; (f) ujson (version 5.10.0) – promotes high-performance serialization and deserialization of JSON objects, significantly outperforming Python's standard json module; (g) python-dotenv (version 1.0.1) – simplifies efficient loading of environment variables from .env files; (h) gunicorn (version 23.0.0) – WSGI HTTP server for Python applications used to run Flask web applications in production environments; and (i) google-cloud-aiplatform (version 1.60.0) – utilized for building, training, and deploying machine learning models through Google Cloud services.

- **Prompt Definition:** A specialized prompt was developed to guide the Gemini model in the specific task of converting natural language questions into geospatial SQL queries. This step included detailed descriptions of tables, columns, and other relevant database information, as well as examples and precise guidelines to ensure the consistency and accuracy of the generated responses.
- **Input Processing:** Advanced functions were implemented for preprocessing user questions, removing ambiguities, and formatting information for compatibility with the Gemini model.
- **Response Management:** A robust system was developed to analyze and validate the SQL queries returned by the Gemini model to ensure query integrity and security before execution.
- **Database Integration:** An abstraction layer was created between the generated SQL queries and the geospatial database to enable the safe and efficient execution of queries.
- **Geographic Data Handling:** Specialized functions were implemented to handle and convert geographic data into GeoJSON format.
- **Error and Exception Handling:** Sophisticated mechanisms were developed to manage errors in query generation or communication with the Gemini API.
- **Performance Optimization:** Caching techniques and other optimization strategies were configured to improve response time and reduce server load.

3.2. Gemini: Definition and Configuration of the Contextual Learning Method

Due to the elevated complexity and the need for scalability in the database, a contextual learning method (in-context learning) of the Gemini model was employed. This emerging technique in machine learning allows language models to process and generate text with greater precision and contextual relevance.

According to Brown et al. (2020), unlike traditional training on large datasets, these models receive specific examples during

inference—i.e., at the moment they are asked to generate a text. This approach is frequently used in advanced chatbots that can maintain natural and contextually relevant dialogues, in automatic translation where the quality of translations is substantially improved by considering the context of sentences, in textual summaries facilitating the creation of concise and accurate summaries of extensive documents while preserving the most relevant information, and in code generation, offering support to programmers in creating code more efficiently.

Radford et al. (2019) played a determining role in advancing language models, establishing a significant milestone in the area. By demonstrating that language models can learn various tasks in an unsupervised manner, the authors paved the way for developing more versatile and robust models, such as those employed in contextual learning. This method allows that, for each new table inserted into the database, it is possible to describe and contextualize it for the model without incurring high computational costs or long processing times, as would happen with fine-tuning.

3.3. Data Collecting and Organization

Due to the specific nature of the project and the methods employed in this study, the database required rigorous construction and standardization criteria. Since the methodology adopted for the Artificial Intelligence training is based on contextual learning, clarity and precision in data description and identification became imperative to ensure the effectiveness of the learning algorithm.

Thus, the first step in building the database involved identifying official sources that met the necessary standards for the preparation and provision of metadata. After careful analysis, three main sources were selected: the National Water Agency (ANA) with 16 datasets; the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) with 3 datasets; and the Energy Research Company (EPE) with 1 dataset. The fundamental criterion for selecting these sources was the availability of data dictionaries, which facilitated the detailed description of the data in accordance with the model's requirements.

Although these sources presented a superior structure compared to other analyzed sources, the 20 selected tables required an additional process of adaptation and normalization before being integrated into the database. For insertion, tools from the GDAL 3.6.4 library were employed, which also performed some preliminary treatment steps. Final adjustments, such as standardization of nomenclature and data type conversion, were executed directly in the PostgreSQL/PostGIS v13.2/3.1 Database Management System (DBMS).

3.4. Creation of the Context

From the metadata, data dictionaries, and detailed information provided by each source, logical descriptions for the databases were developed. These descriptions are essential for the construction of the context file, which plays a fundamental role in learning and interpreting the information by the Artificial Intelligence. Logical descriptions provide a comprehensive view of the database, outlining its purpose and scope, and include a precise breakdown of each attribute, clarifying the meaning of values and specifying the data type stored.

3.5. Gemini: Calibration of the Context

The meticulous definition of parameters in natural language models is essential to ensure consistency, precision, and control in the responses generated. In contexts where accuracy is paramount and randomness must be minimized, the careful adjustment of parameters such as temperature, top-K, and top-P assumes a critical role in shaping token selection, directly influencing the quality and behavior of the text produced. The appropriate choice of these parameters is therefore crucial to meet the specific demands of each application, particularly when deterministic and coherent responses are required.

The temperature parameter controls the degree of randomness in token selection during text generation. Low temperature settings tend to prioritize more probable tokens, resulting in more predictable and less creative outputs. The top-K parameter defines the number of tokens considered in the sampling: a top-K value of 1 ensures that the next selected token is the most probable, while a top-K of 3 ensures that the token chosen is among the top three most likely. Complementary to top-K, the top-P parameter establishes a cumulative probability for token selection, ensuring that only the most probable ones are considered. A low top-P value excludes less probable tokens, further reducing randomness.

In this regard, the model parameters were adjusted to minimize response variability. The temperature was set to 0.1, ensuring highly deterministic responses. The top-K was fixed at 1, ensuring that only the most probable token is selected at each step. The top-P was also adjusted to 0.1, restricting the sampling to the tokens with the highest cumulative probability. Additionally, the output token limit was set at 8,132, allowing responses to be sufficiently detailed without the risk of truncation. These configurations guarantee predictable and controlled behavior, suitable for executing SQL queries.

3.6. Development of the Learning Validation Method

Considering that the purpose of the artificial intelligence application is Natural Language Processing (NLP) for converting queries about geographic data into standard SQL queries, questions were formulated regarding the collected databases to simulate the system’s operation by a non-specialized user, in line with the central problem of this study. The process involved creating a total of 192 questions distributed across different complexity levels to represent the variety of user profiles and experience levels. This approach ensured the simulation of different usage contexts, covering all databases in a non-uniform manner. The focus, in particular, was directed toward more complex data, which are more likely to be queried, enabling a more robust assessment of the system’s functionality.

4. Results Analysis

4.1. NLP Method Evaluation

As previously mentioned, to assess the system’s effectiveness, a comprehensive case study was conducted involving the 20 tables developed from the collected data. In this context, 192 questions in natural language were formulated to explore a wide range of interactions between users and the database. Each of these questions was individually submitted to the Artificial Intelligence, which, in turn, generated corresponding SQL queries.

The generated queries underwent a rigorous two-step validation process. Initially, a database administration expert reviewed the structure and syntax of the queries to ensure compliance with

SQL language standards. Subsequently, the queries that did not present critical issues in their formulation were tested for result accuracy in relation to the sample questions.

The analysis of the results involved categorizing the errors generated by the model during the text-to-SQL processing, which were classified into three main categories: incompatibility errors, lexical errors (as per Guo et al., 2019), and syntax errors. Ultimately, the analysis revealed an overall accuracy rate of 87%. In other words, of the 192 possible interactions between users and the system, 167 resulted in correct answers, while 25 provided unsatisfactory responses. Figure 3 illustrates the error distribution by table, allowing for a detailed analysis of the causes and their implications for the study’s final objective.

Figure 3. Error category per table.

It can be inferred that the inclusion of aggregation clauses, such as the use of GROUP BY, and the need for nested queries exacerbate the conversion process, as these elements are rarely explicitly stated in natural language questions. Therefore, they should also be categorized as incompatibility errors (Zhong et al., 2017; Guo et al., 2019). The following example illustrates this issue:

“What is the unique generation enterprise code of the hydroelectric plant located on the ‘Rio Paraná’ river?”

```
SELECT *
FROM uhe_base_existente
WHERE UNACCENT(lower(rio)) LIKE UNACCENT(LOWER('%Rio Paraná%'));
```

In this example, the generated SQL query includes an inadequate condition, evidenced by the use of the LIKE operator in conjunction with the UNACCENT function, which resulted in a higher number of returned records than expected. The exclusive use of the equality operator would have been the more precise approach to achieving the desired result. Lexical errors, on the other hand, can be attributed to issues such as so-called "out-of-domain" (OOD) words—terms present in the development set but absent from the training set, creating difficulties in token association by the AI model (Guo et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2018b). In this study’s specific context, these errors stem from insufficient or missing information in the database description used to compose the context file, as illustrated below:

“What are all the available details for river stretches in reservoirs with a water balance classified as ‘low’?”

```
SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE UNACCENT(lower(nmres)) IS NOT NULL
```

```
AND UNACCENT(lower(classe)) = UNACCENT(lower('baixo'));
```

The `balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020` table presents a peculiarity in relation to the `nmres` column, which corresponds to the name of the reservoir where the river stretch is located. When a river stretch does not have an associated reservoir, the column stores an empty value. Thus, the use of the `IS NOT NULL` clause on the `nmres` column disregards the river stretches without reservoirs in the query, which constitutes a lexical error. Conversely, syntax errors, also referred to as implementation or generation errors, occur when the SQL query does not adhere to the grammatical or structural rules of the language, resulting in an invalid query that cannot be executed by the Database Management System (Yu et al., 2018). These errors can be caused by various issues, such as the improper use of keywords, the absence of parentheses to define functions or subquery blocks, and even incorrect punctuation. The following example illustrates this type of error:

“Display all details of the river stretches in 2020 with the five highest Q95 water availability values in each water balance class.”

```
SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE classe = 'Baixo'
ORDER BY disp_q95 DESC
LIMIT 5

UNION

SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE classe = 'Mediano'
ORDER BY disp_q95 DESC
LIMIT 5

UNION

SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE classe = 'Alto'
ORDER BY disp_q95 DESC
LIMIT 5

UNION

SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE classe = 'Muito Alto'
ORDER BY disp_q95 DESC
LIMIT 5

UNION

SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE classe = 'Critico'
ORDER BY disp_q95 DESC
LIMIT 5

UNION

SELECT *
FROM balanco_hidrico_quantitativo_microbacia_2020
WHERE classe = 'Intermitente'
ORDER BY disp_q95 DESC
LIMIT 5;
```

To a person without in-depth knowledge of SQL, it might not be immediately evident, but there is a syntax error in this query. This error stems from the improper use of the `UNION` operator, which is used to combine the results of multiple queries. In this specific case, it would be necessary to delimit the queries with parentheses, as SQL requires parentheses to group queries, especially when the `UNION` operator is used in conjunction with clauses such as `LIMIT` and `ORDER BY`. The absence of parentheses can cause SQL to have difficulty correctly grouping the queries and applying the union operations accurately.

Figure 4 shows the general distribution of errors according to the classification in the sample set analyzed.

Figure 4. Proportion by error class.

Although the analysis of the architecture and logic underlying the Text-to-SQL conversion process is not the primary focus of this study, the definition and categorization of errors emerge as a topic of substantial relevance. These errors represent a critical aspect of the natural language-to-SQL conversion and have direct implications for the integration and effectiveness of the proposed system. While incompatibility errors pertain to discrepancies between the intention expressed in the natural language query and the structure of the SQL query generated (Zhong et al., 2017; Guo et al., 2019), lexical errors address terminological divergences (Guo et al., 2019), and syntax errors focus on structural failures that can prevent the correct execution of queries (Yu et al., 2018). Categorizing these errors facilitates the identification and resolution of specific problems that may arise during the query generation process, thereby improving the accuracy and efficiency of Text-to-SQL systems.

4.2. Evaluation of Result Integration

Returning to the primary proposal of democratizing information, a fundamental issue stands out: the difficulty users face when they lack the technical expertise required to analyze databases and generate effective SQL queries.

The complexity of databases poses substantial challenges in formulating SQL queries, particularly for beginners (Taipalus, 2020). To overcome these obstacles, recent studies highlight that systems based on artificial intelligence (AI) have the potential to automate the translation of natural language questions into SQL queries, considerably reducing the need for technical expertise on the part of end-users (Zhong et al., 2017).

In alignment with this perspective, studies such as those by Yu et al. (2018) demonstrate that AI models trained to understand database structures are capable of generating accurate and complex queries, allowing non-experts to interact with data quickly and efficiently. This automation improves response times and accessibility, making data analysis more inclusive and productive, as stated by Xu et al. (2020).

In the field of geotechnologies, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has become a widely disseminated and effective practice. This integration enables the automation of complex processes, such as image classification and spatial data analysis, resulting in a significant increase in productivity and a reduction in the learning curve associated with these technologies (Gorelick et al., 2019).

It is worth noting that expanding the application of this technology to contexts such as the one proposed in this work not only simplifies user interaction with complex geoprocessing tools—such as generating and customizing spatial maps—but also eliminates the need for advanced technical knowledge (Karimi et al., 2018). In this scenario, it can be inferred that the inclusive approach enhances accessibility for inexperienced users, significantly expanding the application of these systems in sectors such as urban planning and environmental management (Li et al., 2020).

4.3. System Representation

The following is a presentation of screenshots of the system interface, offering a detailed view of its structure and functionalities. These visual examples illustrate various aspects of the user’s interaction with the platform, highlighting the layout and design of graphic elements as well as the usability and efficiency of the available operations (Figures 5 to 9).

Figure 5. Highlight for the question: "I want to see the municipality of Belém in the state of Pará."

Figure 6. Highlight for the question: "I want the waterways of the state of Pará."

Figure 7. Highlight for the question: "I want to see the hydroelectric plants on the 'São Francisco River.'"

Figure 8. Zoom when clicking on a record in the table.

Figure 9. Textual responses.

During the tool's testing, deficiencies were detected in the artificial intelligence's ability to properly interpret user queries, resulting in a lack of responses. To mitigate this issue, a new instruction was implemented in the AI context file. Following this modification, when the AI encountered difficulty in understanding the user's request, instead of failing to provide an answer, the tool prompted the user with a clarification, indicating that the request was not understood or that the sought information could not be located. This approach requested the user to reformulate the question with more clarity and detail, thereby facilitating the AI's ability to generate the expected result (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Prompt asking the user to reformulate the question.

5. Conclusion

It is concluded that with the support of artificial intelligence integrated into Geographic Information System (GIS) tools, it is possible to reach a diverse audience, particularly those without specific technical knowledge. The vast amount of information stored geospatially often remains underutilized due to the

complexity and lack of technical skills required for its interpretation. Thus, the development of a system that allows the use of natural language, enabling artificial intelligence to carry out more complex processes, can provide valuable resources for decision-making, promoting the democratization of access to information across different sectors of society.

Throughout this work, several obstacles were identified that compromise the advancement of this and other related initiatives. One of the central challenges lies in the lack of standardization and proper documentation of databases, even when they originate from official sources such as governmental bodies. It is common to encounter inconsistencies in metadata, the absence of data dictionaries compatible with geographic databases, as well as discrepancies between the metadata version and the digital file, which result from a lack of continuous maintenance. Moreover, the correct formulation of the context file used in AI training also presents a significant challenge. The methodology requires detailed and logical descriptions of the structure of each database, becoming increasingly complex as data modeling peculiarities grow. Ideally, each exception must be rigorously described to ensure the accuracy of AI learning.

Despite the initial challenges, this study demonstrates the potential of integrating artificial intelligence and GIS in democratizing access to geographic information. The obstacles faced, such as data quality and complexity, are inherent to pioneering projects and contribute to advancing knowledge in the field. The preliminary results, with an accuracy rate of 86% in query conversion, are promising and suggest the viability of the proposed approach, paving the way for future research and the development of more robust and effective solutions for geographic data analysis.

Future Work

The research presented highlights the transformative potential of artificial intelligence and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in enhancing accessibility and understanding of geographic information. However, the study is still in progress and offers various opportunities for future investigations. The following areas are outlined for exploration and development with a view toward optimizing and expanding the results obtained:

- Improvement of the AI Model: Refine the accuracy of the model; expand the model's capacity to answer more complex questions; adapt the model for different domains and geographic contexts; and conduct continuous evaluation and improvement of the model to not only generate correct queries but also optimize them for efficiency, ensuring better performance in terms of response time and resource use.
- Expansion and Improvement of the Database: Incorporate new data sources; improve the quality of existing data and metadata; and develop ontologies to represent domain knowledge and facilitate the integration of different data sources.
- Development of Tools and Applications: Create an AI-based Geographic Information System (GIS) with an intuitive interface and the ability to answer natural language queries; develop mobile applications to facilitate access to geographic information anywhere and anytime; and integrate the system with other data analysis and visualization tools.
- Impact and Application Analysis: Evaluate the social impact of the tool in democratizing access to geographic information and decision-making; identify new areas of application, such as urban planning, natural disaster management, precision agriculture, among others; and conduct case studies to assess the tool's effectiveness in different contexts.
- Ethical and Social Issues: Ensure privacy and security of geographic data, especially when dealing with personal data; mitigate possible biases in machine learning algorithms, ensuring fairness and equity of the tool; and develop the tool to be accessible to people with different abilities and needs.

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